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The cover depicts the gentle gaze of AI on our precious earth within the cosmic background

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Editorial

Vision with Values

In our advanced culture, we pride ourselves of being able to stand on own feet. We realise that we have, to a large extent, manage to control nature. We are also in the process of manipulating and controlling human body (Human Genome Project) and even our brain (Neuroscience). It is very ambitious enterprise, which will change the way we live and understand ourselves.

In this highly complex scientific and technological world, we need to reformulate our vision and refocus on our values.

Values may be understood as motives behind purposeful action and commitment. They are the ends to which we act and come in many forms. Personal values are personal beliefs about right and wrong and may or may not be considered moral. Cultural values are values accepted by religions or societies and reflect what is important in each context.

To have vision means we have a clear sense of purpose. It means we have a much larger picture of our business, or our life, than simply setting and reaching short term goals and tackling problems as they come along. A vision focusses our own lives on something larger than ourselves and keeps us human, in spite of our struggles and troubles with life.

Values and vision are generally provided by our religious world-view and commitments. They provide us with roots to hold on to the world, especially in troubled times like ours today.

Thus, when our society is advancing technologically and scientifically, we need visions and values, which are both moral and religious. They can help us to cope with the new challenges and uncertainties of our live.

The articles in this volume deal mostly with technological advancement and challenges us to formulate our own world-view, vision and values, which enable us to maintain the sanity in life and sanctity of life.

The Editor